

Some even expressed as 1+1 or 1-2, 1-4, 1-c, 1+2 can also be expressed as 1-3

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ABSTRACT

According to known conclusions, even numbers can be expressed as 1+2, 1+5, 3+2, 1+c. So this paper derives conclusions partial even expressed as 1+1 or 1-2, 1-4, 1-c, 1+2 can also be expressed as 1-3.

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INTRODUCTION

Goldbach's conjecture is that an even number can be represented as a prime number plus a prime number, called "1+1", According to the theory of Chinese mathematician ChenJing run, a large even number can be expressed as one prime number plus no more than two primes product, It is called "1+ 2";There is also Wang Yuan's theory: 1. Large even Numbers can be expressed as the product of two prime Numbers plus three primes product It is called: 3+2; 2.A large even number can be expressed as a prime number plus no more than four prime's product, it is called 1 plus 4;There is also pan cheng dong's theory that large even Numbers can be represented as a prime plus 5 prime's product, called "1+5".

Based on these known conclusions, this paper concludes that some even Numbers that can be expressed as 1+1 can also be expressed as 1-2, 1-4, 1-c, and some even Numbers that can be expressed as 1+2 can also be expressed as 1-3

Theorem 1.1

Chinese mathematician ChenJing run got : a large even number can be expressed as one prime number plus no more than two primes product, It is called "1+ 2"

Lemma 1.2

Partial even numbers can expressed as 1+1 can also be expressed as 1-2.

Certification

All with p subscripts indicate prime numbers
It is known that $1+2$ can indicate all large even numbers proposed by Chen Jingrun,

$$2N_1 - p_1 = p_2 p_3 \quad (2N_1 = p_1 + p_2 p_3 \quad 1+2)$$

There is an even number as the difference between two prime numbers,

$$2N_2 + p_4 = p_5 \quad (2N_2 = p_5 - p_4 \quad 1-1)$$

Because of $2N_1$ representing all large even numbers, N_2 included in N_1 exist, when they are the same. So

$$(2N_1 + p_4) - (2N_1 - p_1) = p_4 + p_1 = p_5 - p_2 p_3$$

$P_4 + p_1$ is $1+1$, $P_5 - p_2 p_3$ is $1-2$, they are equal,

So there are partial even numbers that can be expressed as $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-2$.

Theorem 2.1

There is also Wang Yuan's theory: 1. Large even Numbers can be expressed as the product of two prime Numbers plus three primes product It is called: $3+2$;

Lemma 2.2

The presence of an even number that is expressed as $1+2$ can also be expressed as $1-3$.

Certification

It is known that $3+2$ can represent all large even numbers, proposed by Wang Yuan.

$$2N_1 - p_1 p_2 = p_3 p_4 p_5 \quad (2N_1 = p_1 p_2 + p_3 p_4 p_5 \quad 2+3)$$

There is an even number as the difference between two prime numbers

$$2N_2 + p_6 = p_7 \quad (2N_2 = p_7 - p_6 \quad 1-1)$$

Because of $2N_1$ representing all large even numbers, N_2 included in N_1 exist, when they are the same. So $2N_1 + p_6) - (2N_1 - p_1 p_2) = p_6 + p_1 p_2 = p_7 - p_3 p_4 p_5$
 $P_6 + p_1 p_2$ is $1+2$, $P_7 - p_3 p_4 p_5$ is $1-3$

So there is the existence that $1+2$ can also be expressed as $1-3$.

Theorem 3.1

Wang Yuan's conclusion: A large even number can be expressed as a prime number plus no more than four prime's product, it is called 1 plus 4 .

Lemma 3.2

The presence of a partial even number that is expressed as $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-4$.

Certification

Wang Yuan also proved $1+4$, the same reason: $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-4$.

Theorem 4.1

There is also pan cheng dong's theory that large even Numbers can be represented as a prime plus 5 prime's product, called " $1+5$ ".

Lemma 4.2

The presence of a partial even number that is expressed as $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-5$.

Certification

It is known that $3+2$ can represent all large even numbers, proposed by Pan Chengdong.

$$2N_1 - p_1 = p_2 p_3 p_4 p_5 p_6 \quad (2N_1 = p_2 p_3 p_4 p_5 p_6 + p_1 \quad 1+5)$$

Exist $1-1$ $2N_2 + p_7 = p_8 \quad (2N_2 = p_8 - p_7 \quad 1-1)$

Because of $2N_1$ representing all large even numbers, N_2 included in N_1 exist, when they are the same. So $(2N_1 + p_7) - (2N_1 - p_1) = p_7 + p_1 = p_8 - p_2 p_3 p_4 p_5 p_6$

$$P_1 + p_7 \text{ is } 1+1, P_8 - p_2 p_3 p_4 p_5 p_6 \text{ is } 1-5$$

So there is the existence that $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-5$.

Theorem 5.1

Large even numbers can be expressed as $1+c$, c is a big number.

Lemma 5.2

The presence of a partial even number that is expressed as $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-c$.

Certification

Goldbach guessed that " $a+b$ " was completed: $1+c$, c is a large natural number. According to the above method, there is the existence that $1+1$ can also be expressed as $1-c$.

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